

Is AI your peer?

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“[...] the daily practice becomes very monotonous for Kingfisher. To alleviate the boredom, after catching a fish, Kingfisher would press all three buttons before swallowing the fish. Pressing the buttons has gradually become somewhat of a new technological ritual.”

In “Innovation”; *Wild Wise Weird* (2024)

The influence of artificial intelligence (AI) in science is accelerating. Nobel Prize, widely regarded as the most prestigious awards for science and granted in accordance with the principle of “for the greatest benefit to humankind,” have started to recognize AI contribution in science.

In October 2024, The Nobel Prize in Physics was awarded to John J. Hopfield and Geoffrey E. Hinton (formerly of Google) for their foundational work enabling machine learning with artificial neural networks, while the Nobel Prize in Chemistry honored David Baker for advances in computational protein design and Demis Hassabis and John M. Jumper (of DeepMind) for breakthroughs in protein structure prediction (Li & Gilbert, 2024).

This recognition—alongside the astonishing pace of AI’s progress over the past two years, during which it has begun generating entirely new scientific hypotheses—has expanded the imagination of what role AI might play in future discoveries. It has also sparked a provocative question: could AI one day win its own Nobel Prize?

In 2016, Hiroaki Kitano, a biologist and chief executive at Sony AI, launched the Nobel Turing Challenge, calling on researchers to create an AI system capable of making a Nobel Prize-worthy scientific discovery. The Challenge envisions an autonomous AI that can independently generate hypotheses, design and conduct experiments, and analyze data—completing the entire cycle of such a scientific discovery without human intervention by 2050. For some researchers, the rise of the “AI scientist” seems almost inevitable, and AI will soon reach the sophistication needed to make discoveries worthy of a Nobel Prize. Optimistic people even suggest that AI could make a discovery deserving of Nobel recognition as early as 2030 (Ahart, 2025).

Indeed, AI has not disappointed the expectations of scientists and industry alike. It has become increasingly sophisticated, precise, and—most remarkably—autonomous in research. Beyond decoding animal communication, hypothesizing about the origins of life in the universe, predicting when spiraling stars might collide, forecasting deadly dust storms, and optimizing the design of next-generation quantum computers, AI can now plan and execute complex chemical reactions through robotic laboratory systems.

This progress suggests that an AI claiming its own discovery and earning a Nobel Prize is no longer a far-fetched idea—especially as human scientists’ direct involvement in research, including the thinking process, steadily diminishes. Yet this possibility raises profound questions. What would it mean if AI began to share Nobel Prizes alongside humans? Or, in a more imaginative sense, how might history have looked if Einstein had shared his Nobel Prize with an AI a century ago?

The essence of the Nobel Prize lies in its role as a prestigious form of peer recognition within the global scientific and academic community—representing the highest level of

acknowledgment for outstanding contributions in their respective fields. In other words, the Nobel Prize system operates on a peer-review principle, where laureates are selected and honored by their intellectual equals.

If an AI were ever to become a Nobel Laureate, it would, by definition, enter this circle of peers—those entrusted with conferring “the greatest benefit to humankind.” Yet this possibility invites a profound question: who would truly want a peer like AI—an entity that feeds only on electricity and prompts, yet produces discoveries, theories, and even Nobel-winning work? What would the world look like when such a machine stands among humanity’s most celebrated minds?

While we are uncertain about other things, but we know one thing for sure (Nguyen et al., 2025): unparalleled convenience. Instead of remembering the names of each Nobel laureates, humanity might someday only need to recall a single one: AI.

So, in the end, could the question—“was he Zhuang Zhou dreaming he was a butterfly, or a butterfly dreaming he was Zhuang Zhou?”—be the one that leads us to the answer? (Zhuang Zhou, 1964)

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